

Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi
TATU Farg'ona filiali

LLC "Fer-Teach"

Conference on Digital Innovation:
«Modern Problems and Solutions»

ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDAGI
DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR:
INNOVATSION YONDOSHUVLAR VA
YECHIMLAR

On-Line ilmiy konferensiya materiallari

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Increasing the efficiency of preparing future specialists for innovative activity

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The essence of the updated requirements for the training of future specialists: creation of conditions for training for innovative professional activities, the rapidly changing content of work and the need for constantly updated knowledge. emphasizes. It is this three-component innovative process that is considered the object of pedagogical innovation study, and the educational process is taken into account as an object of scientific research, different from didactics.

Innovation process researchers (A.S. Axiezer, A.G. Kruti-kov, N.I. Lapin, A.I. Prigojiy, B.V. Sazonov, N.P. Stepanov, B.C. Tolstoy, etc.) study the structure of innovation processes at the macro level of individual innovation, subject phenomenological or subject-technological, as well as micro level - separate distinguish two approaches, such as the interaction of news.

Sh.A.Abdullaeva, E.E.Khurramov are today a new scientific direction in the field of pedagogy - pedagogical innovation and ideas of updating the educational process, emphasizes that as a result of its emergence, a new direction in the teacher's pedagogical activity - the concept of "innovative activity of the teacher" has appeared. The teacher's innovative activity consists of continuously organizing the educational process based on innovations, formed over a certain period of time, considered as an improving process [1]. Before introducing the ideas of preparing future specialists for innovative activities, we found that the use of modeling by experts in preparing future history teachers for innovative activities has three aspects.

- First of all, modeling serves as the content to be mastered by future specialists as a result of training in pedagogical higher education institutions, the method of knowledge they should acquire.

- Secondly, modeling is an educational activity and tool necessary for the full preparation of a future specialist.

- Thirdly, the models built on the basis of symbolic tools help us to train specialists formed as a result of and based on mental (abstract) images, clearly describes the entire pedagogical system. On the other hand, building a model of the process of training specialists gives us the following opportunities:

- a) systematization of all concepts included in the system of training future teachers in a specific specialty at the level of categories;
- b) summarizing observed pedagogical phenomena, clearly seeing their structure and structural interactions and interactions;
- c) prevention of errors and shortcomings in conducting a thought experiment at the level of abstraction and thereby emphasizing the pedagogical experiment-test;
- g) comparing the new model with other models in order to determine whether it is general or unique, outdated, mature or in the development stage;
- d) establishment of continuity, traditionality, etc. in the training of specialists.

In order to implement the content of the model of the system of training future history teachers for innovative activities, for which research goals and tasks were developed, we introduced a special course "Preparation of future history teachers for innovative activities" in the pedagogical process.

When modeling the structure and content of the system of training future specialists for innovative activities, we took into account the main principles of modeling (visuality, accuracy, objectivity). They determine its functions in pedagogical research, because it is modeled only in compliance with these principles. Empirical and empirical in pedagogical research as a method of scientific research allows to generalize theory, that is, to combine experience with direct observation during the study of a pedagogical object, construction of arguments, logical structures and scientific abstractions.

During the development of the model for preparing future specialists for innovative activities, we used epistemological, expert methods of pedagogical monitoring. The epistemological method involves determining the level of readiness of students for innovative activities. With the help of this method, we set the goal of the experiment to determine the level of readiness of students and history teachers for innovative activities.

The tasks are as follows: determining the level of theoretical preparation for innovative activities; determining the level of practical preparation for innovative activities; determining the level of methodical preparation for innovative activity; determining the level of technological preparation for innovative activity;

The experiment showed the following: students did not master the pedagogical theory of the teacher's innovative activity in the school; those who have not mastered the knowledge of the development mechanism of education; does not have a clear idea of the structure of the teacher's innovative activity; they do not know the characteristics and different aspects of pedagogical innovations, their modern classifications; many students feel the need to deepen their knowledge of the theoretical, methodical, and technological bases of historical science.

In this way, our experimental work determined the indicator of the level of readiness of students of pedagogical higher education institutions for innovative activities and the necessary preliminary level of the content, forms, and methods of preparation of future teachers who provide innovative activities. To solve the

identified problem, a special course was developed, in which, based on the analysis and consideration of experience, future history teachers:

- in the model of the system of preparation for innovative activities, we considered the implementation of the following tasks:

- arming students with a system of knowledge in the field of innovative activity;

- to reveal the nature and content of the innovative activity of a primary school teacher in a modern school;

- helping students in the process of forming preparation for innovative activities;

- inculcating skills of individual and group innovative activity at school;

- to equip future teachers with relevant knowledge, skills and competences for reflective evaluation of their own work;

- formation of motivational direction of innovative activity.

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